

Studies on alkyd resin from *Pithecellobium dulce*

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Alkyd resin was prepared from *Pithecellobium dulce* seed oil. Kinetics of preparation of seed oil containing alkyd resin was studied. Progress of the reaction was monitored by measurement of acid value of portions of reaction mixture drawn at intervals. The reaction proceeds as second order. Extent of reaction at point of deviation was around 44% and corresponding degree of polymerization is approximately 2.

Due to demand of alkyd resins in surface coating industry, the requirement of oils of plant origin as alternative sources is increasing. *Pithecellobium dulce* (Leguminosae) is a cultivated tree, distributed in central Madhya Pradesh. Seed fatty acid profile has earlier been worked out by us¹. Kinetic analysis of the preparation was taken up to know the reaction conditions.

Results and discussion

The oil has acid value 1.3 and iodine value 148, which compares well with linseed oil, commercially used in the industry. The acid value and iodine value determine the suitability (thin layer of oil to air dry on exposure at ambient temperature). However, linseed oil based films deteriorate on storage due to high unsaturated acid content. The relatively low unsaturated acid content in oils like *Pithecellobium dulce* may overcome this problem.

The acid value of the reaction mixture decreases as the reaction progress (Fig. 1). This may be due to difference in reactivity of α and β hydroxyl groups of glycerol with phthalic anhydride². The reactivity is independent of size of molecules³. The reaction is between functional groups and is given by the expression: $(1 - P)^{-1} = C_0 k_t + 1$, where P is extent of reaction, C_0 is initial concentration, t is time of reaction and k is second order rate constant. In this case, acid value was substituted for concentration. From the expression, it could be said that the plot of $(1 - P)^{-1}$ versus reaction time will be linear if the value of k is uniform throughout. Plot of $(1 - P)^{-1}$ versus reaction time for alkyd sample is linear for 3–4 h and then deviation occurs. Value of second order rate constant k calculated for linear portion is $1.23 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g (mg KOH)}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The other calculated values are: extent of reaction: 44% and degree of polymerization: 1.8 (about 2) at the region where the plot deviated from linearity: between 4th to 5th hour. The deviation indi-

cates the reaction does not follow second order all through. It has also been reported earlier that the rate of esterification is constant at earlier stages of reactions^{4,5}.

Fig. 1. Plots of acid value versus reaction time for the alkyd sample.

Experimental

The seeds were collected from nearby places and authenticated at the Botany Department of University. The oil was extracted with petroleum ether (60–80°C) in a Soxhlet. Alkyd resin was prepared by alcoholysis method⁵. Oil: phthalic anhydride: glycerol (50:28:22) were taken in a round bottom flask fitted with thermometer and condenser. The reactants were stirred constantly. For heating, the heating mantle was set between 230–250°C. Xylene was used as the reflux solvent. Portions of the reaction mixture was taken out at intervals for measuring the acid value.

Extent of reaction and degree of polymerization were given by expressions: $P = C_0 - C_t/C_0$ and $DP = (1 - P)^{-1}$ where C_0 and C_t are acid values at reaction times 0 and t .

Note

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